

Rice-based cropping systems

Insects in an introduced double-cropping pattern of rainfed lowland rice

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A single rice crop transplanted in July is the traditional cropping pattern at the research site of the IRRI-Philippine Bureau of Plant Industry Cropping Systems Program in Oton and Tigbauan, Iloilo, Philippines. The IRRI-BPI team is testing the feasibility of double-cropping of rice by establishing the first crop with the onset of the rainy season (usually in May) after a 3-month dry fallow period. If farmers grow early maturing varieties, there is sufficient rainfall in this nonirrigated area to plant a second rice crop.

Insect pests were monitored in plots that had been treated with insecticide and in untreated plots in six farmers' fields where two crops of IR28 were grown in the introduced pattern. The first crop was wet-seeded in May and the second was transplanted in October.

The first crop was essentially insect

Insect occurrence and benefit from insecticide protection on the first (wet-seeded IR28) and second (transplanted IR28) crops of an introduced rice double-cropping pattern in a rainfed lowland environment. Oton and Tigbauan, Iloilo, Philippines, 1976.

Crop	Defoliation (%)	Untreated		Rice bugs (no./sq m)	Yield (t/ha)	
		Stem borer (%)	Whiteheads		Untreated plots	Treated ^a plots
First ^b	4	2.6	2.3	1.2	5.1	5.1
Second ^c	22	5.4	7.4	3.7	3.9	5.0

^a2 kg a.i. carbofuran (Furadan 3 G)/ha incorporated in the soil before planting, followed by 4 spray applications of 0.75 kg a.i. monocrotophos (Azodrin 16.8 EC)/ha.

^bAv. of 6 fields planted in May.

^cAv. of 6 fields planted in October.

free; both protected and unprotected plots yielded 5.1 t/ha (see table). Because the crop was established early with the first rains, it escaped pest buildup.

The second crop was attacked by the same insect complex that normally attacks the single rice crop. The key insects were rice caseworm *Nymphula depunctalis* (whose larvae defoliate the crop), rice green-homed caterpillar *Melanitis leda ismene*, and rice skipper *Pelopidas mathias*. Minor insects were stem borers (predominantly white rice borer *Tryporyza innotata*) and rice bug

Leptocorisa acuta. The pests increased on the first rice crop as well as on the grassy weeds that proliferated in fallow fields with the onset of rains before the July puddling of the single crop. The yield difference between the insecticide-protected and unprotected plots (5.0 vs 3.9 t/ha) was significant in the second crop.

The fact that the first crop requires no insect control makes the double-rice pattern attractive to farmers whose cash resources to purchase insecticides are limited. ❧

A boro and deep-water rice relay cropping pattern in Bangladesh

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Farmers in Bangladesh, encouraged by high yielding varieties, better irrigation, higher boro yields, and less risk of flood damage, have shifted 0.5 million of the estimated 2 million ha of deep-water rice to boro cultivation. A cropping pattern in which a boro crop is followed by deep-water rice is not possible for most farmers because the late boro harvest (late April to May) interferes with the

establishment of the deep-water rice crop. A study to determine the feasibility of growing deep-water rice in addition to modern boro rice on the same land in 1 year by relay cropping was conducted. Boro rice was planted in the dry season (late December) in a deep-water field near the Bangladesh Rice Research Institute (BRRI). The flood water rose to 1.5 m deep and lasted from mid-June to October in 1977.

The effect of different plant and row spacings on boro rice yield and on the establishment of deep-water rice seedlings was studied. The effect of different relay planting methods and nitrogen applications on yields of

deep-water rice after boro harvest was also investigated.

Boro yield did not significantly differ between traditional 20 × 20-cm spacing and paired-row spacing (15 cm between hills and rows, 45 cm between paired rows). But paired-row spacing made the broadcast aman crop easier to plant at the boro crop's flowering stage, resulted in less damage to the boro crop at harvest, and increased broadcast aman yields (see table). Topdressing of 40 kg N/ha increased deep-water rice yields by 100% in all boro spacing plots. The yields of broadcast aman rice were low because the exceptionally heavy rains in May and June flooded the sprouted deep-water rice

The effect of plant spacing, row spacing, and nitrogen application on the yields of boro rice and of a relay crop of deep-water rice, Bangladesh.

Spacing (cm)	Boro rice yield (t/ha)		N application (kg/ha)	Deep water rice (Hbj. Aman IV) (t/ha)
	BR6	BR3		
20 × 20	3.2	5.1	0	0.3
			40	0.7
30 × 15	3.0	4.9	0	0.5
			40	1.0
15 × 15 × 49 ^a	3.0	5.0	0	0.6
			40	1.2

^a15 cm between hills and rows, 45 cm between paired rows.

seeds and reduced the plant stand.

In another study, no significant difference was found between using sprouted seeds and transplanting 30-day-old seedlings of deep-water rice. The plot was not deeply flooded, however, and deep-water rice yields averaged a respectable 1.4 t/ha.

The experiment's indicate that relay cropping of boro and deep-water rice has a definite potential for increasing rice production in some areas of Bangladesh.

But the choice of boro variety and spacing, the timing and method of planting of deep-water rice, and the amount of fertilizer needed for good stands and yields require more study. Major factors that determine the success of the cropping pattern and that vary from site to site include the timing of the flood, the moisture status during establishment of deep-water rice, and nutrient availability. ❧

Expected rice yields in rainfed systems

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The IRRI cropping systems program is investigating strategies for multiple cropping of rice in rainfed and partially

irrigated systems through appropriate choice of variety and cultural practices. Major considerations are planting dates, growth duration of rice varieties, tillage methods, planting methods (direct seeding or transplanting), and rainfall distribution. To assess farmers' yield expectations with their present

technology, yields of more than 900 farmer-managed plots of rainfed and partially irrigated rice, including 556 plots of improved and 422 plots of traditional varieties, were examined by date of harvest. The data were obtained from daily farm records kept in 1975-76 and 1976-77 by 130 farmers in Batangas, Iloilo, and Pangasinan provinces, Philippines. The times of onset and decline of bimodal rainfall patterns are similar at all the sites. The improved varieties were planted in lowland fields; most were single crops. Most traditional varieties were also single crops, but some were grown on upland fields.

The solid portions of free-hand curves in Figure 1 represent the 5-week moving averages of rice yields by week of harvest. The first peaks of the improved and traditional variety curves are the moving averages of 83 and 35 plots, respectively. The second peaks are based on 65 observations of improved varieties and 73 of traditional ones, and the intervening troughs are based on 117 and 78 observations, respectively. The lowest number of observations in any 5-week period was 22, which constitutes the moving average centered on week 33 on the improved variety curve. A maximum of 154 points are averaged for week 39, also lying on the improved variety curve. Points on the dashed portion of the improved variety curve are based on a low number of observations and mainly represent the few relatively better irrigated plots in the sample. The dashed portion of the traditional rice curve mainly represents the yields of 153 upland rice plots at the Batangas site.

While the actual rainfall pattern shifts from year to year, it generally follows a bimodal distribution with a major peak in July and a minor peak in October. We have not attempted, however, to rigorously identify possible relationships between climate and yield. The data suggest that highest total production on lowland can be expected by direct-seeding an early maturing improved variety in mid-May for harvest in early September, then transplanting a second crop for harvest in late December. Ongoing studies indicate that the availability of power and labor, and the timing of the actual onset

1. Five-week moving average of yields of improved and traditional rice varieties by date of harvest. One hundred and thirty farmers' fields in Batangas, Pangasinan, and Iloilo Provinces, Philippines, 1975-76 and 1976-77.